

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

First white paper on community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications

Deliverable D2.6

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

On June 30, 2020, the Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling was held as a virtual event within the framework of ESIWACE2, the Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe.

The workshop organized by Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC), Graham Riley (UNIMAN), Carlos Osuna (METEOSWISS) and Sandro Fiore (CMCC), was hosted by DKRZ with the local support by Dela Spickermann and Florian Ziemer under the supervision of the ESIWACE2 Coordinator Joachim Biercamp. The workshop was funded by the Horizon 2020 project ESIWACE2. Due to the situation with COVID-19, the event was held as a virtual conference with approximately 143 participants mainly from Europe and the US, but also from Brazil, India and Israel.

The workshop brought together scientists from the fields of earth system modeling, machine learning, exascale hardware/computing, and programming models, informing them about the latest developments in these fields and fostering a mutual exchange, also involving HPC experts. The agenda of the workshop was organized in three sessions, for a total of 17 talks, focusing on: Exascale hardware (Session 1), Programming models and hardware interplay (Session 2) and Machine Learning (Session 3).

Two sessions were organised in the morning (for EU speakers), while the third one was scheduled in the afternoon to allow US speakers to give talks during their local daylight hours. All talks were held as a videoconference, whereby the presentation slides as well as the speaker were usually broadcasted live to all participants via screen sharing. Questions for the speakers were collected in online documents during the talk and directed to the speakers by the chairpersons afterwards. As main outcome of this workshop, a set of community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications was produced. The guidelines are related to the areas of Exascale hardware, Programming models & hardware interplay and Machine Learning. A second white paper is planned during the ESIWACE2 project to harden, update and extend the main findings collected in these three areas from this first workshop.

2. Conclusion & Results

The workshop provided a very good overview on emerging technologies for weather and climate Modelling focussing on exascale hardware, programming models and hardware interplay and machine learning. It delivered as main outcome a set of community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications. The workshop was accessible to a broad audience, especially to those scientists who did not have funding to attend on-site events. Moreover, the carbon footprint of the event was drastically reduced due to the virtual format that required neither travel nor accommodation for the participants. To make the interaction easier between the speakers and the overall audience and give the opportunity to manage a larger number of questions despite the short time dedicated to the Q&A, questions for the speakers were collected in three Google Docs. This resulted in a successful question time for all three sessions, with a lively exchange of information between the speakers and the audience.

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3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	YES
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	YES

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	YES
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	YES
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	YES
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	YES
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	YES
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	YES

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Community Guidelines

This deliverable is the first white paper on community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications. The guidelines provided in the following subsections on the areas of Exascale hardware (Section 4.1.1), Programming models and hardware interplay (Section 4.1.2) and Machine Learning (Section 4.1.3) represent the main outcome of the ESIWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling (see Section 4.2).

4.1.1 SESSION 1 — EXASCALE HARDWARE

This section summarises the key messages from the Exascale Hardware talks.

- There are initiatives to build exascale hardware in the US, Europe and China so a variety of systems can be expected to emerge.
- Test systems, some based on emulators with heavy diagnostic support, can be expected to appear for use by scientists over the next one to three years. Several test chips and some hardware emulators are becoming available.
- Systems will be heterogeneous and essentially modular with a mixture of CPUs (existing and new), GPUs (a key component of many early systems), wide-vector architectures (probably based on RISC-V) and other accelerators including FPGAs.
- Software will have to be organised so that components are targeted to the most effective hardware, where possible.
- There will be a range of CPU chips with products being based, at least, on Intel, AMD and ARM technologies along with some specialist chips.
- The developments in Machine Learning ML accelerators, e.g. TPUs, is of interest for two reasons: first, to support the many current efforts to exploit ML and AI technologies, such as deep learning, in weather and climate models; and, second, in exploring whether and how the reduced precision and high performance provided by ML accelerators can be exploited to accelerate the existing, traditional numerical algorithms used in weather and climate codes.
- As exascale-level hardware becomes available, achieving exascale performance in weather and climate codes will require further improvements in the performance and scalability of existing algorithms as well as new numerical techniques, such as ML-based algorithms. Also, re-coding of appropriate software components to target accelerators and to improve overall software scalability, probably through the use of DSLs, will be required (as discussed in the Programming models session of the workshop).
- The recent RISC-V long vector standard will likely have a prominent role in Exascale. A RISC-V emulator exists to help users' early co-design efforts.
- Application instrumentation and analysis tools will be key to helping with the transition of software to the emerging architectures. Several existing tools are being extended to address scalability issues to help with this.
- In terms of programming, there appears to be growing confidence that MPI + OpenMP can be expected to be available on early Exascale systems, and it will initially be sufficient as previous scaling concerns may not be as serious as thought (see also the Programming models section).
- It is to be anticipated that the role of cloud and edge computing will increasingly form a component of the overall weather and climate computing ecosystem, and will be used to perform tasks that complement computing targeted to Exascale HPC systems.
- Co-design is necessary but in practice is very difficult to achieve, primarily due to the different time scales involved in software and hardware development. Application instrumentation and analysis tools and (rapidly developed) hardware emulators may be the way forward to address this.

- Dynamic energy management by applications will become increasingly important.

4.1.2 SESSION 2 — PROGRAMMING MODELS AND HARDWARE INTERPLAY

This section summarises the key messages of the session on programming models and hardware interplay.

- Holistic approaches to the power/performance problem challenges for the Exascale are considered by the community.
- Newer node architectures that reduce latencies are essential: accelerators with peer-to-peer communication, direct access to IO and interconnects that minimise the communication distance.
- Applications need to consider the data-flow problem in order to maximise data locality and minimize data transfer.
- DSLs are being developed and will play an important role within the community in order to solve the performance portability problem. They separate concerns between science and parallelisation and optimisation. Significant progress has been shown by several DSLs in their applicability to weather and climate models: Dawn, PSyclone and ExaSlang.
- DSLs are developed as modularised toolchains with different levels of abstractions.
- While MPI+X has been a most widespread programming model choice for HPC applications, Exascale is not business as usual. We can expect that MPI+X continues to be a popular choice. However, alternatives of emerging parallel programming models like PGAS, parallel C++ frameworks like SYCL, Kokkos/RAJA or new programming models like Julia will more usage while the community targets scalability and portability.
- In addition to the aforementioned emerging programming models for applications, workflows for environments like PyCOMPS will integrate HPC simulations and data analytics with support of hybrid systems, dynamic workflows, data streamings, etc. and will provide the portability required for diverse and heterogeneous HPC systems.

4.1.3 SESSION 3 — MACHINE LEARNING

This section summarises the key messages of the session on machine learning.

- Simple Deep Learning can be used to accelerate forecast pipelines.
- Using Encoder-Decoder networks for predicting mean and standard deviation in ensemble systems yields higher accuracy than using small ensemble statistics. This is promising for increasing performance in large-scale settings.
- There are a large number of application areas throughout the prediction workflow in weather and climate modelling for which machine learning can really make a difference; the weather and climate community is still at the beginning of exploring the potential of machine learning (and in particular deep learning).

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- Machine learning could not only be used to improve models, it could also be used to make them more efficient on future supercomputers.
- Machine-learning accelerators could be useful to speed up components of weather and climate models; however, there are limitations for the application of black box solutions within weather and climate models and challenges that need to be addressed.
- Machine learning is an appealing approach for subgrid parameterisations; however, there are issues to be considered regarding conservation laws, physical invariants, and physical laws. Potential solutions based on hybrid Physical+ML approaches appear as powerful tools to tackle this.

4.2 Workshop on Emerging technologies for weather and climate modelling

The program committee of the workshop consisted of Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC), Graham Riley (UNIMAN), Sandro Fiore (CMCC), Carlos Osuna (METEOSWISS), who were in charge of organizing the event and of Dela Spickerman (DKRZ) and Florian Ziemer (DKRZ) in charge of hosting the virtual event and provide technical support.

The workshop saw 17 talks by international speakers structured into three sessions. The full agenda is attached to this report. In the following subsections (4.2.1-3), speaker name, biography and abstract are reported for each talk (with the only exception of the abstract related to Talk 1 in Session 1).

4.2.1 SESSION 1: EXASCALE HARDWARE

Talk 1: A useful definition of exascale computing for weather and climate modelling

Speaker: Thomas Schulthess (CSCS)

Biography: Thomas Schulthess is Director of the Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS) at Manno. As CSCS director, he is also full Professor of Computational Physics at ETH Zurich. Thomas Schulthess studied Physics at ETH Zurich and earned his doctorate in 1994 with a thesis on surface physics in which he combined experiment and supercomputing simulations. He subsequently continued his research in the US and published around seventy research papers in the best journals of his field. His research interests are focused on magneto electronics, nanoscience, and transition metal oxide materials, as well as the application of ultra-scale computing in these areas.

Abstract: *not available*

Talk 2: Future HPC systems made in Europe

Speaker: Jesus Labarta (BSC)

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Biography: Professor Jesús Labarta has been full professor of Computer Architecture at UPC since 1990 and was Director of CEPBA-European Center of Parallelism at Barcelona from 1996 to 2005. Since its creation in 2005, he has been the Director of the Computer Sciences Research Department within the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). During his 35-year academic career, Prof. Labarta has made significant contributions in programming models and performance analysis tools for parallel, multicore and accelerated systems, with the sole objective of helping application programmers to improve their understanding of their application's performance and to improve programming productivity in the transition towards very large-scale systems. His research team has been developing performance analysis and prediction tools (Paraver and Dimemas) and pioneering research on how to increase the intelligence embedded in these performance tools. He has also been a driving force behind the task-based StarSs programming model, which gives runtime systems the required intelligence to dynamically exploit the potential parallelism and resources available. His team has influenced the evolution of the OpenMP standard with the OmpSs instantiation of StarSs, and, in particular, its tasking model. He has constantly tried to incorporate his vision and ideas into industrial collaborations. Currently Prof. Labarta is the leader of the Performance Optimisation and Productivity (POP) EU Center of Excellence where users (both academic and SMEs) from a very wide range of application sectors receive performance assessments and suggestions for code refactoring efforts. He also leads within the EPI project the activities (hardware and software) on the RISC-V vector accelerator in Nov 2018, he was awarded by The Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) and IEEE Computer Society (IEEE CS) with the ACM-IEEE CS Ken Kennedy Award for his seminal contributions to programming models and performance analysis tools for high performance computing. He is the only non US Researcher receiving this award.

Abstract: Squeezing performance out of complex and continuously changing architectures is difficult. Refactoring huge codes for next-generation machines is OK... But only until a next-next generation comes. And continuous refactoring is a dangerous loop that domain scientists rightly want to avoid. Trying to foresee the weather forecasting community's curiosity, I try to answer the questions, "Which will be the next HPC system? What impact will have on our codes? Which is the status of future computing systems in Europe?"

The talk guided the audience through the European Processor Initiative (EPI) project and in particular its RISC-V vector accelerator targeting HPC. Since the audience should be familiar with HPC applications, the idea was to start from the performance analysis of weather forecasting HPC codes to show how to get insights and architectural implications that can influence the design of future HPC systems.

Talk 3: European Processor Initiative: the European approach for exascale ages

Speaker: Jean-Marc Denis (ATOS/EPI)

Biography: Since the beginning of 2020, Jean-Marc is the Chief of Staff of the Innovation and Strategy Division at Atos. In addition, since the middle of 2018, Jean-Marc has been elected as Chair of the Board of the European Processor Initiative (EPI). Prior to that, Jean-Marc Denis took different positions in the HPC industry. After five years of research in the development of new

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solvers for the Maxwell equations at Matra Defense (France) as mathematician from 1990 to 1995, Jean-Marc Denis held several technical positions in the HPC industry between 1995 to 2004 from HPC pre-sales to Senior Solution Architect. Since mid of 2004 Jean-Marc has worked at Bull SAS head Quarter (France) where he has started the HPC activity. In less than 10 years, the HPC revenue at Bull exploded from nothing in 2004 to 200M€ in 2015, making Bull the undisputed leader of the European HPC industry and the fourth in the world. From 2011 to the end of 2016, Jean-Marc has led the worldwide business activity with the goal of consolidating the ATOS/Bull position in Europe and making ATOS/Bull a worldwide leader in Extreme Computing with a footprint in Middle-East, Asia, Africa and South America.

From 2018 to 2020, Jean-Marc has been the head of Strategy and Plan at Atos/Bull, in charge of the global cross-Business Unit Strategy and of the definition of the 3 years business plan.

In 2016 and 2017, Jean-Marc was in charge of the definition of the strategy for the BigData Division at ATOS/Bull. In his position, his role is to define the global approach for the different BigData business lines covering HPC, Legacy (mainframe), Enterprise computing, DataScience consulting and Software.

In parallel to his activities at ATOS/Bull, since 2008, Jean-Marc Denis has taught “Supercomputer Architecture” concepts in Master 2 degree at the University of Reims Champagne Ardennes (URCA), France.

Abstract: The rise of artificial intelligence in HPC, associated with the data deluge, combined with the transition from monolithic applications toward complex workflows and dataflows lead the HPC community, especially the hardware architects, to reconsider how the Exascale supercomputers are designed. Furthermore, the advent of hybrid computing, defined as the combination of in-house with cloud computing significantly impacts design metrics.

This presentation discussed the transition from existing homogenous to Exascale class modular architectures. The consequences on the compute components including the general-purpose processor and the associated accelerators were addressed. Ultimately, all these considerations lead to the guidelines having ruled the design of the European microprocessor that will empower the European Exascale supercomputers.

Talk 4: LUMI: the EuroHPC pre-exascale system of the north

Speaker: Kimmo Koski (CSC/LUMI)

Biography: Dr. Kimmo Koski is Managing Director at CSC, the Finnish IT Center for Science, since 2004. Earlier work experience includes 10 years at CSC in various positions, 4 ½ years at Nokia Research Center and one-year visiting period in CERN in Switzerland. His doctoral work was at Helsinki University of Technology in 1996 about Metacomputing technology. Koski has been active in building European HPC and data infrastructure through involvement in major EU initiatives, such as EUDAT, EOSC, PRACE and lately especially in EuroHPC.

Abstract: The EuroHPC initiative is a joint effort by the European Commission and 31 countries to establish a world-class ecosystem in supercomputing to Europe (read more at <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/>). One of its first concrete efforts is to install the first three

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"precursor to exascale" supercomputers. Finland, together with 8 other countries from the Nordics and central Europe, will collaboratively host one of these systems in Kajaani, Finland. This system, LUMI, will be the one of the most powerful and advanced computing systems on the planet at the time of its installation. The vast consortium of countries with an established tradition in scientific computing and strong national computing centers will be a key asset for the successful infrastructure. This talk discussed the LUMI infrastructure and its great value and potential for the research community.

Talk 5: Towards a modular supercomputing architecture for exascale

Speaker: Estela Suarez (Jülich Supercomputing Centre)

Biography: Dr. Estela Suarez has been a Senior Scientist at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre since 2010. Her research focuses on HPC system architectures and co-design. As leader of the DEEP series of EU-funded projects she has driven the development of the Cluster-Booster and the Modular Supercomputing Architectures. Additionally, since 2018 she leads the co-design efforts within the European Processor Initiative. She holds a PhD in Physics from the University of Geneva and a Master degree in Astrophysics from the Complutense University of Madrid.

Abstract: Reaching Exascale compute performances at an affordable budget requires increasingly heterogeneous HPC systems, which combine general purpose processing units (CPUs) with acceleration devices (e.g. graphic cards (GPUs) or many-core processors). The Modular Supercomputing Architecture, developed within the EU-funded DEEP project series, orchestrates all these resources at system-level, organizing them in compute modules. The goal is to provide cost-effective computing at extreme performance scale fitting the needs of a wide range of Computational Sciences.

In a modular supercomputer each application can dynamically decide which kinds and how many nodes to use, mapping its intrinsic requirements and concurrency patterns onto the hardware. Codes that perform multi-physics or multi-scale simulations can run across compute modules thanks to a global system-software and programming environment. Application workflows that execute different actions after (or in parallel) to each other can also be distributed in order to run each workflow-component on the best suited hardware, and exchange data either directly (via message-passing communication) or via the file-system. This talk described the Modular Supercomputing Architecture – which constitutes the central element in the JSC’s roadmap to Exascale – including its history, its hardware and software elements, and its current and upcoming implementations.

4.2.2 SESSION 2: PROGRAMMING MODELS AND HARDWARE INTERPLAY

Talk 1: The Euroexa system architecture for exascale

Speaker: John Goodacre (University of Manchester)

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Biography: Prof. John Goodacre: University of Manchester; UKRI Challenge Director, Digital Security by Design; Chief Scientific Officer and Co-founder Bamboo Systems Group Ltd.

John holds a Professorship in Computer Architectures from the School of Computer Science at the University of Manchester having recently transitioned from being the Director of Technology and Systems in the Research Group at ARM Ltd. Having successfully bid for a UK Gov. Industrial Strategy Challenge Fund, he was appointed by UK Research & Innovation as the Challenge Director with responsibility to deliver the £200M programme of funded activities and associated research agenda with goals to fundamentally improve the digital security of computer systems. He is also co-founder and Chief Scientific Officer at Bamboo Systems Limited, a manufacturer of an innovative class of Arm based servers. His career included the realisation of the first scalable commodity telephony platform, the introduction of the first real-time online collaboration tools that shipped in Microsoft Exchange 2000, while more recently, he was responsible for the design and introduction of the ARM MPCore multicore processors and associated technologies. His roles today extend across academic, industrial and government sectors. His research interests include web-scale servers, Exascale efficient systems and secure and ubiquitous computing. He sits on various advisory boards and is a frequent conference speaker.

Abstract: Euroexa is a H2020 Towards Exascale FETHPC co-design project that is undertaking a holistic view across the entire hardware infrastructure and software stack to reconsider many of the inherited assumptions about how the resources of a computer connect and interact so as to maximize computational efficiency. This talk offered a journey from how energy is provided to the system, how the electronics and processing subsystems interact, the computational models and its acceleration and interconnect through to what the system does to enable a meaningful reuse of the computational byproduct - heat.

Talk 2: Developing DSLs in ESIWACE2

Speaker: Rupert Ford (STFC)

Biography: Rupert Ford started working in High Performance computing in November 1990 at the University of Manchester and stayed there for 22 years. In 2012 he moved to STFC Daresbury Laboratory and is currently working in STFC's Hartree Centre. The majority of his research and development over the past 25 years has been in Earth System Modelling and Integrated Assessment where he has developed the BFG coupling and the PSyclone DSL systems. He is currently involved in the UK LFRic project and co-leads the future technology work package in the EU ESIWACE2 Centre of Excellence project.

Abstract: ESIWACE2 is a European Union H2020-funded Centre of Excellence whose primary mission is to prepare weather and climate models for the Exascale era. One of the areas of investigation in ESIWACE2 is Domain Specific Languages (DSLs). DSLs are of interest as they allow the specification and coding of the natural science to be separated from its parallelisation and optimisation. Such a separation therefore offers the potential of both higher scientific productivity and performance portability. The work on DSLs in ESIWACE2 is focused on GridTools and PSyclone and can be split into 4 categories 1) demonstration of the use of DSLs on real models

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on pre-exascale machines, 2) comparison of the two approaches through selected benchmarks, 3) interoperability between the two DSLs and 4) evaluation of the performance of DSLs compared with hand-tuned solutions. This talk introduced the work proposed in these 4 categories in more detail and presents the progress to date.

Talk 3: Whole program code generation for ocean simulation

Speaker: Harald Köstler (University of Erlangen-Nuremberg)

Biography: Prof. Dr. Harald Köstler works at the Chair for System Simulation at the University of Erlangen-Nuremberg in Germany and leads the group for HPC software design. His research interests include software engineering concepts especially using code generation for simulation software on HPC clusters, multigrid methods, and programming techniques for parallel hardware, especially GPUs. Main application fields are Lattice Boltzmann methods for computational fluid dynamics, particulate flows using the discrete element method, phase-field models for solidification processes, variational methods in imaging, and discontinuous Galerkin methods for Ocean simulation.

Abstract: Code generation is one way to increase productivity for both users and developers when dealing with large software packages. Separation of concerns is achieved by formulating applications on different levels of abstraction. The talk presented a short overview of different code generation approaches and the ExaStencils project, that started as a domain-specific language for multigrid solvers on structured grids. Meanwhile, the external DSL ExaSlang is mature enough to express full application models for Ocean simulation. As an example, the talk showed the whole-program generation for the shallow water equations on block-structured grids created from a real-world geometry and using a higher discontinuous Galerkin discretisation. The generated code is highly scalable on current supercomputers and portable to GPU and CPU architectures.

Talk 4: Exascale programming models: beyond “MPI+X”

Speaker: Simon McIntosh-Smith (University of Bristol)

Biography: Simon McIntosh-Smith is a computer scientist and Professor of High Performance Computing at the University of Bristol in the UK. His background in computer architecture has led research interests in performance portability, parallel programming models for heterogeneous systems, and emerging architectures. He is the PI for the world’s first production Arm-based supercomputer, Isambard, and chairs the hardware and enabling software programme within ExCALIBUR, the UK’s Exascale initiative.

Abstract: Exascale systems are expected to be exotic creatures, with heterogeneous architectures, millions of degrees of parallelism, and deep memory hierarchies. What are the most promising programming models for these Exascale machines? Is it inevitable that MPI is going to be used for inter-node parallelism while OpenMP, Kokkos or similar models are used

within the nodes? Or will other approaches, such as PGAS finally have their day? The talk explored the options, and reviewed what is already known about the programming models announced for Exascale systems around the world. Some predictions and recommendations for developers of scientific codes aiming for Exascale were also presented.

Talk 5: Programming dynamic workflows in the exascale era

Speaker: Daniele Lezzi (BSC)

Biography: Dr. Daniele Lezzi is Senior Researcher in the Computer Sciences department of Barcelona Supercomputing Center. He holds a PhD in Information Technology Engineering (2007) from the University of Salento, Italy. His research interest covers High Performance, Distributed and Cloud Computing and programming models. In particular, this research addresses the design of programming frameworks for the porting and execution of scientific applications on computing infrastructures like Clouds, Fog-to-Edge. He is currently involved in the BioExcel Center of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research and in the Landsupport initiative.

Abstract: Today, developers lack tools that enable the development of complex workflows that include HPC simulations and modelling with data analytics (DA) and machine learning (ML), in a unique programming framework. Current environments are in fact fragmented in multiple components, using different programming models, with different processes for computing and data management. This talk presented the recent activities of the Workflows and Distributed Computing group at BSC to develop a workflow software stack and an additional set of services to enable the convergence of HPC and big data analytics (HPDA) and machine learning in scientific and industrial applications. This framework allows the development of innovative, adaptive and dynamic workflows that efficiently make use of the heterogeneous computing resources and also leverage innovative storage solutions. An application of the framework for a biomolecular dynamics use case was also presented, to describe how the tools allow developers to run huge executions making an efficient use of large supercomputers such as the ones that are to be available in the coming years and thus reaching the pre-exascale era.

Talk 6: LFRic and PSyclone: utilising DSLs for performance portability

Speaker: Iva Kavcic (UK Met Office)

Biography: Dr Iva Kavcic is a Senior Scientific Software Engineer in the LFRic team within the UK Met Office. She received a PhD degree in Geophysics with Meteorology from the University of Zagreb, Croatia, where she worked on parameterisation of turbulence in the stable boundary layer. Her later work as a PostDoc at the University of Exeter, UK, focused on research and development of the ENDGame and GungHo dynamical cores of the Met Office's forecast model. Her current area of work is interfacing LFRic and PSyclone, from design to implementation and testing of PSyclone features in LFRic, as well as managing PSyclone releases in the Met Office systems. Her research interests include numerical methods for geophysical fluids and translation

of scientific and numerical concepts related to atmospheric modelling into computational domain.

Abstract: LFRic is the new weather and climate modelling system being developed by the UK Met Office to replace the existing Unified Model in preparation for exascale computing in the 2020s. LFRic uses the GungHo dynamical core and runs on a semi-structured cubed-sphere mesh. The design of the supporting infrastructure follows object-oriented principles to facilitate modularity and the use of external libraries. One of the guiding design principles, imposed to promote performance portability, is “separation of concerns” between the science and parallel code.

Parallel code in LFRic is generated by PSyclone with the support of LFRic infrastructure, which provides APIs to support the distributed memory parallelism via libraries such as YAXT. PSyclone provides general (e.g. shared memory parallelism using OpenMP) as well as LFRic-specific optimisations. For example, PSyclone can enhance the use of distributed memory parallelism in LFRic via optimisations such as asynchronous-halo-exchange transformation and redundant computation into annexed dofs. The talk gave more examples of the impact of PSyclone on the LFRic performance.

4.2.3 SESSION 3: MACHINE LEARNING

Talk 1: Deep learning for post-processing ensemble weather forecast

Speaker: Torsten Hoefler (ETH, Zürich)

Biography: Torsten is professor of Computer Science at ETH Zurich where he directs the Scalable Parallel Computing Laboratory. He has served as the lead for performance modelling and analysis in the US NSF Blue Waters project at the National center for Supercomputing Applications of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.

He has held visiting positions at Argonne National Laboratories, Sandia National Laboratories, and Microsoft Research Redmond. He is very active in the application areas of weather and climate simulations as well as Machine Learning with a focus on Distributed Deep Learning.

Abstract: Quantifying uncertainty in weather forecasts typically employs ensemble prediction systems, which consist of many perturbed trajectories run in parallel. These systems are associated with a high computational cost and often include statistical post-processing steps to inexpensively improve their raw prediction qualities. The talk proposed a mixed prediction and post-processing model based on a subset of the original trajectories. The model implemented deep learning methods to account for non-linear relationships that are not captured by current numerical models or other post-processing methods. Applied to global data, these mixed models achieve a relative improvement of the ensemble forecast skill of over 13%. The talk demonstrated that this is especially the case for extreme weather events on selected case studies, showing an improvement in predictions by up to 26%. It was also shown that, by using only half the trajectories, the computational costs of ensemble prediction systems can potentially be reduced,

allowing weather forecasting pipelines to run higher resolution trajectories, and resulting in even more accurate raw ensemble forecasts.

Talk 2: Machine learning for weather predictions at ECMWF

Speaker: Peter Dueben (ECMWF)

Biography: Peter is the Coordinator of Machine Learning and AI activities at ECMWF (the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) and holds a University Research Fellowship of the Royal Society. His research interests are in the area of numerical weather and climate modelling, machine learning, and high-performance computing. He is a work-package leader of the ESIWACE 2 Centre of Excellence, and a co-author of the ESCAPE 2 project.

Abstract: The talk outlined how machine learning, and in particular deep learning could help to improve weather predictions in the coming years and presented an overview of the work on machine learning methods that is ongoing at the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts. Weather prediction requires modelling the Earth System — a huge system that consists of many individual components and shows chaotic behaviour for which conventional tools are often struggling to provide satisfying results. On the other hand, a huge amount of data is available from both observations and modelling. Therefore, a large number of machine learning applications are currently tested in order to improve the different components across the workflow of numerical weather predictions. However, whether these approaches will succeed is still unclear as there are also a number of challenges for the application of machine learning tools in weather predictions that were discussed in the talk.

Talk 3: Efficiently constraining parameter uncertainty in a General Circulation Model using targeted data

Speaker: Oliver Dunbar (Caltech)

Biography: Oliver is an applied mathematician, currently working as postdoc on Environmental Sciences and Engineering at the California Institute of Technology. He works primarily in the Climate Modeling Alliance (CliMA) under Prof. Tapio Schneider and Prof. Andrew Stuart, using Bayesian uncertainty quantification and machine learning techniques to improve climate model prediction.

Abstract: Climate prediction relies upon closure models for subgrid scale processes that are unfeasible to resolve globally. These closures feature model parameters, and there is a strong interest in quantifying the uncertainty of these parameters. Regional data may be available and can be used to learn about these parameters. The research activities are focused on efficiently finding regions of optimally informative data, useful for learning. The talk considered a closure for moist convection within an idealized aquaplanet general circulation model (GCM). A Calibrate-Emulate-Sample (CES) philosophy was used to feasibly perform uncertainty

quantification on closure parameters, making use of Gaussian process emulation. The talk introduced Bayesian design to the CES framework to locate optimally informative data subsets.

Talk 4: Hybrid modeling: best of both worlds?

Speaker: Pierre Gentine (Columbia University)

Biography: Pierre is an associate professor in the department of Earth and Environmental Engineering. He obtained his MSc and PhD from MIT.

He works on land-atmosphere interactions, convective clouds, and surface hydrology using conceptual models, numerical models and a wide range of data analysis tools.

Pierre is recipient of several awards from the NSF, NASA and DOE, as well as the American Geophysical Union Global Environmental Changes and American Meteorological Society.

Abstract: In recent years, we have witnessed an explosion in the applications of machine learning, especially for environmental problems. Yet for broader use, those algorithms may need to respect exactly some physical constraints such as the conservation of mass and energy. In addition, environmental applications (e.g. drought, heat waves) are typically focusing on extremes and on out-of-sample generalisation rather than on interpolation. This can be a problem for typical algorithms, which interpolate well but have difficulties extrapolating. The talk showed how a hybridisation of machine learning algorithms, imposing physical knowledge within them, can help with those different issues and offer a promising avenue for climate applications and process understanding.

Talk 5: Climate informatics: machine learning for the study of climate change

Speaker: Claire Monteleoni (Colorado University)

Biography: Claire is Associate Professor of Computer Science at the University of Colorado Boulder, which she joined in 2018, following positions at University of Paris-Saclay, CNRS, George Washington University, and Columbia University. She completed her PhD and Masters in Computer Science at MIT and was a postdoc at UC San Diego. She holds a Bachelor's degree in Earth and Planetary Sciences from Harvard. Her research on machine learning for the study of climate change helped launch the interdisciplinary field of Climate Informatics. In 2011, she co-founded the International Workshop on Climate Informatics, which turns 10 years old in 2020, and has attracted climate scientists and data scientists from over 20 countries and 30 U.S. states.

Abstract: Despite the scientific consensus on climate change, drastic uncertainties remain. Crucial questions about regional climate trends, changes in extreme events, such as heat waves and mega-storms, and understanding how climate varied in the distant past, must be answered in order to improve predictions, assess impacts and vulnerability, and inform mitigation and sustainable adaptation strategies. Machine learning can help answer such questions and shed light on climate change. The talk gave an overview of climate informatics research carried out at Colorado University, focusing on challenges in learning from spatiotemporal data and climate

model projections, along with semi- and unsupervised deep learning approaches to studying rare and extreme events, and downscaling temperature and precipitation.

Talk 6: Machine-learning of moist physics parameterizations for a climate model using coarse-graining of global cloud-resolving model output

Speaker: Noah Brenowitz (Vulcan Inc.)

Biography: Noah is a Senior Machine Learning Scientist for Climate Modeling at Vulcan Inc, working to improve climate models with machine learning techniques.

He holds a Ph.D. in Atmosphere-Ocean Science and Mathematics from the Courant Institute of Mathematics. Noah’s research lies at the intersection of applied mathematics, machine learning, and atmospheric science. He is interested in applying machine learning techniques to improve the representation of sub-grid-scale processes in coarse resolution atmospheric models. In addition, he also studies the fundamental dynamics behind the organization of large-scale moist convective processes in the tropics.

Abstract: Climate models cannot affordably simulate small-scale physical processes so they must approximate the effect of important phenomena like clouds, precipitation, and turbulence with parameterizations. Unfortunately, uncertainty in these sub-grid-scale parameterizations limits our faith in our coarse-resolution climate models and contributes to well-known climate model biases. Traditional parameterizations designed by human experts have changed little in decades despite a recent explosion in our ability to observe the Earth-system and run explicitly-resolved simulations. The brute-force solution to this problem is to decrease the grid-spacing of atmospheric models until they can resolve individual thunderstorms, but this is not yet feasible for climate-scale simulations. Machine learning (ML) presents another path forward by replacing traditional schemes with nonlinear regression models trained from shorter high-resolution simulations or observations. This talk introduced the attempts to build machine learning parameterizations for use in increasingly complex simulations of the atmosphere. The talk was particularly focused on how ML parameterizations can play nicely with fluid-mechanics simulations and on interpreting their behavior. While these efforts are targeted on improving atmospheric models, similar techniques could be applied to sub-grid-scale problems throughout the Earth sciences.

5. References (Bibliography)

Link to the event web page:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/events/virtual-ws-on-emerging-technologies/virtual-ws-on-emerging-technologies>

Link to the agenda, abstracts and presentations:

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<https://www.esiwace.eu/events/virtual-ws-on-emerging-technologies/presentations/final-agenda-with-abstracts-and-slides>

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Due to the situation with COVID-19, the event associated with this white paper was run as a virtual conference.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

Knowledge sharing and capacity building in this white paper and the associated workshop contribute to the EU strategy of becoming a world leader in HPC. Indeed, the talks were related to the future HPC systems made in Europe, the European Processor Initiative (EPI), EuroHPC pre-exascale supercomputers in Europe and Supercomputing architecture for exascale. Insights on hardware and software were provided at large scale on HPC systems both from a computational and scientific standpoint.

8. Sustainability

This deliverable is the first white paper on community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications. The second one is planned during the ESIWACE2 project to harden, update and extend the main findings collected in these three areas from this first workshop.

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

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This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The workshop was widely announced to the target audience and well received as can be seen by the large number of participants. The slides of all presentations were available for download for all registered participants. With the permission of the speakers we published most of the presentations at <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/virtual-ws-on-emerging-technologies/presentations/final-agenda-with-abstracts-and-slides>, using the ESIWACE webpage as central point of access for information regarding HPC in Weather and Climate. The public dissemination of this white paper with the key findings via Zenodo will further contribute to the uptake of the findings.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

Please note that we are committed to Open Access: either go for the golden OA or for the green OA.

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <i>open access</i> be provided to this publication?

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

n.a.

10. Annex 1: Workshop Agenda

ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate

Modelling

June 30, 2020

10.30 - 18.45 CEST

Agenda

10:30-10:45	<i>VC Available for test</i>	
10:45-10:50	Welcome	G. Riley, G. Aloisio
10:50-12:30	Session 1 – Exascale hardware	Chair: Graham Riley
10:50-11:10	A useful definition of exascale computing for weather and climate modelling	Thomas Schulthess (CSCS)
11:10-11:30	Future HPC systems made in Europe	Jesus Labarta (BSC)
11:30-11:50	European Processor Initiative: the European approach for Exascale ages	Jean-Marc Denis (ATOS/EPI)
11:50-12:10	LUMI: the EuroHPC pre-exascale system of the North	Kimmo Koski (CSC/LUMI)
12:10-12:30	Towards a Modular Supercomputing Architecture for Exascale	Estela Suarez (Jülich Supercomputing Centre)

12:30-14:00	<i>Lunch Break</i>	
14:00-16:00	Session 2 – Programming models and hardware interplay	Chair: Carlos Osuna
14:00-14:20	The Euroexa system architecture for exascale	John Goodacre (University of Manchester)
14:20-14:40	Developing DSLs in ESIWACE2	Rupert Ford (STFC)
14:40-15:00	Whole program code generation for Ocean simulation	Harald Köstler (University of Erlangen-Nuremberg)
15:00-15:20	Exascale programming models: beyond “MPI+X”	Simon McIntosh-Smith (University of Bristol)
15:20-15:40	Programming dynamic workflows in the Exascale Era	Daniele Lezzi (BSC)
15:40-16:00	LFRic and PScyclone: Utilising DSLs for performance portability	Iva Kavcic (UK Met Office)
16:00-16:30	<i>Coffee Break</i>	
16:30-18:30	Session 3 – Machine Learning	Chair: Giovanni Aloisio
16:30-16:50	Deep Learning for Post-Processing Ensemble Weather Forecast	Torsten Hoefler (ETH, Zürich)
16:50-17:10	Machine learning for weather predictions at ECMWF	Peter Dueben (ECMWF)
17:10-17:30	Efficiently constraining parameter uncertainty in a General Circulation Model using targeted data	Oliver Dunbar (Caltech)
17:30-17:50	Hybrid modeling: best of both worlds?	Pierre Gentine (Columbia University)
17:50-18:10	Climate Informatics: Machine Learning for the Study of Climate Change	Claire Monteleoni (Colorado University)

18:10-18:30 Machine-learning of moist physics parameterizations for a climate model using coarse-graining of global cloud-resolving model output Noah Brenowitz (Vulcan Inc.)

18:30-18:45 **Wrap up and closing session**

Program Committee

Giovanni Aloisio, Graham Riley, Sandro Fiore, Carlos Osuna

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